

Title	Author	No. in Storey catalogue	BL correct shelf number
On the pronunciation of the Qur'ān		4037	IO Bijapur 272
Tafsīr-i tawzīḥ		3086	Delhi Arabic 18
al-Fawz al-kabīr fī uṣūl al-tafsīr	Shāh Valī Allāh Dihlavī	3099	Delhi Arabic 279d
Fālnāmah		4047	Delhi Arabic 367
On the abrogated and abrogating verses of the Qur'ān		4014	Delhi Arabic 61b
Faḥ al-Raḥmān bi-tarjamāt al-Qur'ān	Shāh Valī Allāh Dihlavī	3097	Delhi Arabic 64a
Tafsīr Āyat al-kursī	Nūr al-Dīn Muḥammad al-Vā'iz	3087	Delhi Arabic 77a
On the recitation of the Qur'ān	Muḥammad Ma'sūm	4031	Delhi Arabic 93b
On the reading of the Qur'ān		4032	Delhi Arabic 93c
Qavā'id al-Qur'ān	Yār Muḥammad ibn Khudādād Samarqandī	4017	Delhi Arabic 93d
Commentary on Sūrah 78		4009	Delhi Arabic 949
Commentary on Sūrah 78		4010	Delhi Arabic 949
Tarjumān-i Qur'ān	al-Jurjānī	4011	Delhi Arabic 984
Faḥ al-Raḥmān bi-tarjamāt al-Qur'ān	Shāh Valī Allāh Dihlavī	3096	Delhi Arabic 9d
Tafsīr-i Sūrat al-Fātiḥah	Mu'tin al-Dīn Farāhī	3080	Delhi Persian 1
Commentary on Sūrahs 36 and 67		3088	Delhi Persian 11
A discussion of Sūrah 51:57	Rafī' al-Dīn Dihlavī	4006	Delhi Persian 1145
Risālah-i shaqq al-qamar	Rafī' al-Dīn Dihlavī	4007	Delhi Persian 1145
Intikhāb-i Tafsīr-i Sūrah-i Muzzammil	Shāh Ṭā-Hā Quṭb al-Dīn Qādirī Katānavī	4008	Delhi Persian 1169
On talismanic virtues of the Qur'ān		4046	Delhi Persian 1182
Khavāṣṣ-i Sūrah-i Yūsuf		4051	Delhi Persian 1182
Tafsīr Fātiḥat al-Kitāb	Nizām al-Dīn Thānaysarī	3090	Delhi Persian 1184b
Commentary on Sūrah 12		3085	Delhi Persian 12
Āṣār al-akhyār	'Alī ibn Ḥasan Zavārī	3093	Delhi Persian 14
Tafsīr-i Shāh va Shāh-i tafāsīr	Mullā Shāh	3091	Delhi Persian 1420
Tafsīr-i Sūrah-i Yūsuf	Mullā Shāh	3092	Delhi Persian 1420
Faḥ al-Raḥmān bi-tarjamāt al-Qur'ān	Shāh Valī Allāh Dihlavī	3095	Delhi Persian 15
Khulāṣah al-Manhaj	Kāshānī	3084	Delhi Persian 17
Tafsīr-i Faḥ al-'Azīz	'Abd al-'Azīz Dihlavī	4003	Delhi Persian 22A
Tafsīr-i Faḥ al-'Azīz	'Abd al-'Azīz Dihlavī	4004	Delhi Persian 22C
On the circumstances which led to the revelation of particular parts of the Qur'ān and on those verses which abrogate or are abrogated by others		4013	Delhi Persian 23
Khulāṣah al-Manhaj	Kāshānī	3083	Delhi Persian 24
al-Fawz al-kabīr fī uṣūl al-tafsīr	Shāh Valī Allāh Dihlavī	3098	Delhi Persian 25
Baḥr al-'ulūm al-Islāmīyah	Ghulām Muṣṭafa Thānaysarī Dihlavī	4001	Delhi Persian 2A
Baḥr al-'ulūm al-Islāmīyah	Ghulām Muṣṭafa Thānaysarī Dihlavī	4002	Delhi Persian 2B
Nūr al-karīmatayn	Qamar al-Dīn Awrangābādī	4000	Delhi Persian 30
Vasīlat al-qabūl ila Ḥaḥrat al-Rasūl	'Abd al-Raḥīm ibn Naṣr Allāh 'Alavī	3094	Delhi Persian 31
Durr al-farīd fī 'ilm al-tajwīd	Ṭāhir Iṣfahānī	4015	Delhi Persian 32
On the reading of the Qur'ān		4033	Delhi Persian 32
Qavā'id al-Qur'ān	Yār Muḥammad ibn Khudādād Samarqandī	4016	Delhi Persian 33a
Najāt al-qārī	Mfir Sayyid 'Alī	4023	Delhi Persian 33c

On the 83 obligatory pauses	Yār Muḥammad ibn Khudādād Samarqandī	4019	Delhi Persian 33d
On the rewards for reading Sūrahs of the Qurʾān		4052	Delhi Persian 33e
Zubdat al-qirāʾah	Qivām al-Dīn Muḥammad Bukhārī	4030	Delhi Persian 33f
Metrical list of signs indicating pauses		4044	Delhi Persian 33f
On the correct reading of the Qurʾān		4038	Delhi Persian 33g
Qavāʾid al-Qurʾān	Yār Muḥammad ibn Khudādād Samarqandī	4018	Delhi Persian 33h
al-Takmil fi qirāʾah al-tanzīl		4026	Delhi Persian 34a
Maʾrifat al-qirāʾah	ʿAbd al-Raḥmān ibn Yūsuf	4024	Delhi Persian 34c
On the pronunciation of the Qurʾān		4034	Delhi Persian 34d
Nāẓm-i ḥāsim		4022	Delhi Persian 34e
Maʾrifat al-qirāʾah	ʿAbd al-Raḥmān ibn Yūsuf	4025	Delhi Persian 34e
Metrical list of Sūrahs of the Qurʾān		4045	Delhi Persian 34g
Mavāhib-i ʿalīyah	Husayn Vāʾiz Kāshifī	3081	Delhi Persian 3A
Mavāhib-i ʿalīyah	Husayn Vāʾiz Kāshifī	3082	Delhi Persian 3B
Tafsīr-i Yaʿqūb Charkhī	Yaʿqūb Charkhī	3078	Delhi Persian 5B
Tafsīr-i Niẓām al-Dīn Thānaysarī		3089	Delhi Persian 6
Tafsīr-i Yaʿqūb Charkhī	Yaʿqūb Charkhī	3079	Delhi Persian 8
On talismanic virtues of the Qurʾān	ʿAbd al-ʿAlī Birjandī	4048	Delhi Persian 84A
On talismanic virtues of the Qurʾān	ʿAbd al-ʿAlī Birjandī	4049	Delhi Persian 84B
Maqṣūd al-qāriʾ	Nūr al-Dīn Muḥammad Qāriʾ	4021	IO Islamic 1435
Zīnat al-qāriʾ	Nuṣrat ibn ʿUmar Sikandar	4027	IO Islamic 1435
Zīnat al-qāriʾ	Nuṣrat ibn ʿUmar Sikandar	4028	IO Islamic 1435
On the reading of the Qurʾān	Luṭf Allāh Aḥmad	4039	IO Islamic 1435
Metrical memoria technica for abbreviations used to indicate Readers		4041	IO Islamic 1435
Metrical memoria technica for abbreviations used to indicate Readers		4042	IO Islamic 1435
Metrical list of signs indicating pauses		4043	IO Islamic 1435
Maqṣūd al-qāriʾ	Nūr al-Dīn Muḥammad Qāriʾ	4020	IO Islamic 1435
Metrical memoria technica for abbreviations used to indicate Readers		4040	IO Islamic 1435
Tafsīr al-Sūrābādī	Sūrābādī	3077	IO Islamic 3838-40
On talismanic virtues of the Qurʾān		4050	IO Islamic 4296
A discussion of Sūrah 51:56	Rafīʾ al-Dīn Dihlavī	4005	IO Islamic 4297
Lughāt-i Qurʾānī		4012	IO Islamic 4297
On the pronunciation of the Qurʾān		4035	IO Islamic 4298
On the pronunciation of the Qurʾān		4036	IO Islamic 4300
Manẓar al-qāriʾ	Ḥāfiẓ Akhṣarī	4029	Mss Panj B 42